

The Impact of Performance Appraisal and Appropriate Reward on Employees' Performance

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Abstract

The goals of the organization are yardstick for measuring organization performance; therefore, HRM practitioners adopt the use of performance appraisals in the evaluation of their employee performance in conformity with the organization's set goals since employee performance is fundamental to the organization's success. The application of human inclination to judge without a structured appraisal system does not guarantee the decision made is accurate, lawful, and defensible. Despite all the research that has been conducted in the area of staff appraisal, there has been little done on the impact of performance appraisal on employee performance as it relates to staff reward in tangent with the appraisal exercise. Therefore, this research is aimed at determining if a relationship exists between an employee's performance appraisal and their productivity and also determine the impact of a well-structured appraisal process on employee satisfaction, with a view to establishing the impact of staff appraisal and appropriate reward on staff motivation. The research uses questionnaire to obtain information from the sampled respondents. Furthermore, the researchers reviewed published articles on the subject. The research instrument was subjected to descriptive and inferential statistics. The research hypotheses were tested using regression analysis tools. Regression is used to test the relationship that exists between a dependent variable and two or more independent variables. The research established that the significance of a well-structured appraisal system cannot be overemphasized in an organization. Hence, the university management should ensure appropriate rewards are put in place in conformity with the appraisal result, with a view to creating a formidable workforce, enhancing cordiality between staff and students, and further enhancing the productivity of the workers.

Keywords: Management, appraisal, commensuration, employee, performance, human resource management.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Goals are set by organizations and pursued rigorously. In a bid to achieve such a goal, organizations set targets for individuals, groups, or departments and work assiduously towards achieving them. In view of this, the organization's management is tasked with the responsibility of employing techniques and expertise through efficient planning, organizing, directing, and controlling the operations, all aimed at achieving set targets. The Human Resource Management (HRM) department of the organization is saddled with the responsibility of ensuring efficient management of the organization's workforce. They are responsible for the recruitment and retention of good employees, as well as the training and development of employees to boost their productivity and efficiency with a view to promoting the overall success of the organization (Anwar & Abdullah, 2021).

The goals of an organization are yardstick for measuring organization performance; therefore, HRM practitioners adopt the use of performance appraisals in the evaluation of their employee's performance since their performance is fundamental to the organization's success (Daniel, 2019). The desirable performance of employees that are considered significant to the organization's needs is dependent upon positive job attitudes like job satisfaction and commitment. Thus, negative attitudes pose a threat to the attainment of organizational goals (Olasokan and Toki, 2021).

Performance appraisal is an indispensable aspect of an organization; hence, it is significant to the organization's survival and productivity. In view of this, performance appraisal continues to garner more interest among researchers and organizations alike (Daoanis, 2012). In order for organizations to experience improved development and employee job satisfaction, they invest huge sums of money in reward and recognition with a view to enhancing their productivity (Francis, 2020). It is also important to mention that performance appraisals are also used by organizations to ensure employees are cognizant of their performance improvement and growth, as well as their abilities and potential. Therefore, a performance appraisal system has a substantial impact on other aspects of human resources (HR) and its significant to an organization in its entirety; hence, an employee appraisal that is well orchestrated will help reconcile the needs of an organization and the needs of the organization's employees (Daniel, 2019).

Performance appraisal has been widely adopted in organizations to measure and evaluate the performance of employees across all levels. Both the public and private sectors have been known to employ formal employee appraisal systems increasingly. Performance appraisal has been the focus of a flurry of research activity for decades. Different scholars have discovered and stated that effective performance appraisal is an important element of the effectiveness of employee management in an organization. There has also been a continued use of performance appraisal systems by business and industry, with recent surveys indicating that 74 percent to 89 percent of firms have a formal performance appraisal system (Murphy & Cleveland, 2010).

Performance appraisal gained popularity for a number of different purposes, including human resource decisions, feedback, and program evaluation (Cleveland, Murphy, and Williams, 2010). Performance appraisal is an annual exercise conducted by organizations in order to determine an employee's overall contribution to the organization's performance. This appraisal of performance is done using aspects such as time management at work, quality of work done, quantity produced, cost incurred to produce results, or any other credible and mutually agreed standard or measure (Armstrong, 2014). Performance appraisal answers many questions concerning the job by coming up with solutions and a path to be followed, which sometimes results in improved performance.

The global economic depression has put major constraints on government budgets recently, most importantly in public services, which has no doubt led to non-proportional rewards for staff appraised. However, due to the significance of human resources in attaining organizational goals, this act of checks and balances in organizations cannot be neglected. However, performance appraisal may sometimes result in negative effects in organizations if not properly managed, which has become an issue of concern in many organizations that have not put in place the right tools for staff performance measurement for appropriate alignment with organizational goals. Researchers also cite loopholes in the appraisal system and warn of the dangers it poses to management and their subordinates.

Many organizations are faced with the challenge of maximizing staff performance; therefore, performance appraisal seems inevitable. In the absence of structured appraisal systems, management will tend to judge the work performance of employees in an informal way. The human inclination to judge without a structured appraisal system can create serious ethical, motivational, and legal issues in the organization. Without a structured appraisal system, there is no chance of ensuring that decisions made are fair, accurate, lawful, and defensible. Despite the significance attached to performance appraisal among human resource managers and the quantum of research carried out on the subject matter (Rosemond et al., 2010), little has been done as it relates to the impact of performance appraisal on employee performance as it relates to the reward of staff in tangent with the appraisal exercise. It is against this background that this research is aimed at analyzing the impact of performance appraisal and appropriate compensation on employee performance in the public service. To achieve this aim, the research will adopt the following objectives:

1. To determine if a relationship exists between an employee's performance appraisal and their productivity
2. To determine the impact of a well-structured appraisal process on employee satisfaction
3. To examine the impact of staff appraisal and appropriate reward on staff motivation

1.2 Research Hypotheses

H₀: No relationship exists between an employee's performance appraisal and their productivity.

H₀: A well-structured appraisal process does not have a significant impact on employee satisfaction.

H₀: Staff appraisal and appropriate reward do not have a significant impact on staff motivation.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This study contributes immensely to the existing study on performance appraisals and, most importantly, as it relates to public service. The research will establish if there is a compensating reward for the various appraisal exercises carried out. The research outcome will propose a structured appraisal system that will help address a series of ethical, motivational, and legal issues that often arise in the organization after most staff performance appraisal exercises. The research findings will also serve as a source of reference for other research in the field of study in the future and will be

significant in bringing to the attention of human resource managers the factors to note in designing appraisal systems, with a view to making it a worthwhile exercise.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Literature Review

2.1.1 Performance Appraisal

Armstrong and Baron (2014) indicate that performance is a multidimensional construct whose measurement is based on several factors. Performance appraisal is one of the most daunting tasks that the HR department in most organizations has to carry out on a regular basis. If performance appraisal is not carried out perfectly, it can result in a ripple effect among staff, which may result in an unfair and ineffective result. According to Armstrong (2014), line managers have the most important duty to see that performance management succeeds. The role of senior management is to manage and effectively deploy organizational resources in such a manner that they fulfill organizational objectives. There are many tools, frameworks, and techniques that assist managers in meeting their obligations.

2.1.2 Performance Appraisal and Its Purpose

Performance management represents a strategic and integrated approach that is geared towards delivering organizational success by improving the performance capabilities of both individuals and teams (Armstrong, 2014). Performance appraisal is concerned with the clarification of employees' work expectations, helping with individual employee growth and the collective growth of the entire workforce, as well as ensuring that pay structure design incorporates performance. It ensures that employees have an awareness of how organizations expect them to perform in relation to organizational goals after their performances are evaluated (Lindquist, 2015)

2.1.3 Staff appraisal and a value-based approach

Human resource managers strive to put in place the right performance measurement system, which is value-based, that helps them set agreed-upon performance goals and achieve the desired outcomes. Performance measurements generate data that is used to gauge the direction in which the organization is headed and allow the organization to design, control, and account for staff performance as laid out in the organization strategy (Henri, 2014). A study conducted by Blasé and Blasé in 2013 in the United States outlined that a number of employees report being victims of unfair performance evaluation, while some complained that the commiseration is not usually in tangent with the outcome of the appraisal exercise, which may sometimes be attributed to financial constraint, thereby leading to resentment among staff.

It is evident that the outcome, the information used, the interpersonal dynamics between an evaluator and the one being evaluated, and the procedure adopted for the performance appraisal may impact the employee negatively. Unfair performance reviews may lead to the employee being fired, and the emotional stress of losing a job as a result of an unsatisfactory performance appraisal can result in physical manifestations ranging from exhaustion to cardiac and repository issues (Blase & Blase, 2013). According to Lindquist (2015), in developed countries, the fairness of performance appraisal procedures may be associated with fair outcomes. However, according to Fisher (2007), this is not an appropriate use of the performance appraisal system because its outcomes determine the appropriateness of a pay increase.

2.1.4 Impacts of Performance Appraisal on Employees' Attitudes

Studies on the impacts of performance appraisal on employees' attitudes emphasize the need for feedback (Shrivastav & Sapra, 2012) and rewards (Gichuhi, Abaja, & Ochieng, 2012). Shrivastav and Sapra (2012), in a study to investigate the impacts of performance appraisal on employees' attitudes, revealed the relevance of performance appraisal to organizations but also emphasized the need to give feedback to employees due to the positive impact that will have on their performance. They assert that feedback after an appraisal helps strengthen communication between supervisor and employee and also motivates the employee. The study also underscores the role performance appraisal plays in guiding employees to work towards attaining organizational goals and their own goals as well. Poorly undertaken performance appraisals, they warn, could have detrimental effects on the organization by causing employees to perform worse.

Finally, research on salespeople asserts that giving clear explanations of the criteria used in evaluating employees and giving employees the chance to partake in designing appraisals has a positive relationship with their commitment. However, if the employees' roles in the organization are not clearly defined, it will have a negative impact on commitment (Rosemond et al., 2010). Performance appraisal may also be positively related to affective commitment, thus supporting the arguments about communicating superordinate goals (Latham, 2003). Moreover, developmental performance appraisal is concerned with giving employees a sense of belongingness and that sense of being valued by their teams and the organization at large, as this is vital in making employees more affectively committed to the organization (Levy & Williams, 2004).

2.1.5 Performance Appraisal Approaches

Organizations may adopt different approaches, which can be traced to the categorization by Creamer and Janosik (1999), which comprises behavior-based approaches and result-focused approaches. Creamer and Janosik (1999) describe behavior-based approaches as the type of performance appraisal that employs the use of specific factors of performance in the evaluation of employees. These include rating scales and the forced choice method. Another type that fits under the behavior-based approach is the behavioral checklist, which outlines specific criteria or targets an employee must meet. The behaviors may vary according to the particular type of job under assessment. This method is regarded as favorable because it avoids comparing the performance of one employee with the performance of another employee but rather focuses on performance yardsticks for each employee (Diya Jose, 2013).

Secondly, results-focused approaches place emphasis on the results the appraisals brings. An example of a result-based approach that is widely used is management by objectives (MBO). MBO evaluates performance objectively, and it is a modern form of performance appraisal. With MBO, managers and their employees have a discussion, and both parties agree on which goals to achieve and when to achieve them (Diya Jose, 2013). Daoanis (2012) also discusses 360-degree appraisals and psychological appraisals. She describes a 360-degree appraisal as one that takes an all-inclusive approach. It ensures that all parties related to the employee, that is, the manager, supervisor, and team members, give feedback on the employee's performance. It also makes use of employee profiles and reports. Apart from all these, in-depth feedback from the employee himself is also used.

Psychological appraisals, on the other hand, are very useful in placing employees in teams as they use a psychological approach in evaluating psychological traits such as how an employee analyzes issues, his reasoning ability, his emotional stability, and his intellect.

2.1.6 Performance Appraisal Criteria

Performance appraisal assesses three basic categories of employee performance: traits, behaviors, and results (Grobler et al., 2011).

1. **Trait-based behavior:** Focus on the personal characteristics of the employee (e.g., loyalty, dependability, creativity, and communication skills). Here, the focus is on who a person is and not what he or she does or accomplishes on that job. However, trait appraisals are often not valid as performance measures because they tend to be ambiguous and highly subjective (Bateman and Snell, 2013).
2. **Behavior-based criteria:** Although subjective, this approach focuses more on observable aspects of performance. They are developed in response to the problems of trait appraisals. These scales focus on specific, prescribed behaviors that can help ensure that all parties understand what the ratings are really measuring. Because they are less ambiguous, they can also help provide useful feedback (Bateman and Snell, 2013). These are concerned with specific behaviors that lead to job success. For example, instead of ranking leadership ability (a trait), the rater is asked to assess whether an employee exhibits certain behaviors (e.g., "works well with co-workers; Grobler et al., 2011).
3. **Results or outcome-based criteria:** These tend to be more objective and can focus on production data, such as sales volumes, units produced, or profits. Results-based outcomes focus on what was accomplished or produced rather than how it was accomplished or produced. One approach to results appraisals, management by objectives (MBO), involves a subordinate and a supervisor agreeing in advance on specific performance goals. It is important to note that this type of criterion is not appropriate for every job, and it is often criticized for missing important aspects of the job, such as quality.

Cascio (2013) asserts that proper performance management must do three things: set goals, decide how to measure performance, and provide regular assessments of progress. He argues that if an organization intends to encourage its employees to perform at a higher quality, it's important to provide a sufficient number of rewards that employees' value in a timely and fair manner. He emphasized that companies should not offer rewards that employees are not concerned about. Biswajeet (2009) asserts that a PA does not merely measure the performance of the people but has many other benefits. The benefits of a successful appraisal system can be summarized as follows:

a) For the appraisee

- Better understanding of his or her role in the organization, what is expected, and what needs to be done to meet those expectations. This includes the security of knowing that they are doing the job that is agreed upon.
- Framework for gauging personal performance.
- a clear understanding of his or her strengths and weaknesses in order to develop into a better performer in the future.
- Increased motivation, job satisfaction, and self-esteem.
- Opportunity to discuss work problems and how they can be overcome.

- Opportunity to discuss aspirations, guidance, and the support or training needed to fulfill these aspirations.
- Improved working relationships with superiors.

b) For the management

- Identification of performers and non-performers and their development towards better performance
- Opportunity for preparing employees for assuming higher responsibilities.
- Opportunity to improve communication between the employees and management.
- Identification of training and developmental needs
- Generation of ideas for improvement.
- Better identification of potential and formulation of career paths.

c) For the organization

- Improved performance throughout the organization.
- Creation of a culture of continuous improvement and success.
- conveying the message that people are valued.

2.1.7 Steps in Developing a Performance Appraisal System

The specific steps followed in developing a PA system will vary somewhat from organization to organization. Nonetheless, the general guidelines discussed here will be followed by most employers when developing an appraisal system (Grobler et al., 2011):

- **Determine performance requirements:** In the first step of the process, administrators must determine what skills, outputs, and accomplishments will be evaluated during each appraisal. These may be derived from specific job descriptions, or they may be a uniform set of employee requirements included in all PAs. Policymakers must determine exactly what areas of performance are going to be reviewed and how this area relates to the organization's strategic goals.
- **Choose an appropriate appraisal method.** Several methods may be used to appraise performance, and no single method is best for all organizations. The manner in which a supervisor conducts PAs is strongly determined by the method. Within an organization, different appraisal methods may be used for different groups, such as production, sales, and administrative employees.
- **Train supervisors:** A critical step in the PA process is training supervisors (or other raters) to make sure that they prepare fair and accurate appraisals and effectively communicate the evaluation to the employees. Unfair ratings may result in charges of discrimination, loss of employee morale and productivity, or inaccurate appraisals, which lead to poor compensation or staffing decisions.
- **Discuss methods with employees:** Prior to appraisal interviews, supervisors should discuss with employees the method that will be used. This discussion should specify which areas of performance will be evaluated, how often, how the evaluation takes place, and its significance to the employees. The use of appraisals varies greatly; some organizations tie pay and promotion directly to the PA, whereas others conduct appraisals only in a perfunctory manner to meet some broad goals or policies.
- **Appraise according to job standards:** PAs should evaluate the employees' work according to predetermined work requirements. Comparison with specific requirements indicates what employees have or have not done well. The supervisor's feelings about the employee should not affect the appraisal. Feelings cannot be evaluated; they are only mental constructs and may be biased. By discussing employees' observed and documented behavior, the supervisor focuses the appraisal on the concrete and actual performance of the employee.
- **Discuss appraisal with employees:** In some organizations, appraisal discussions are omitted whenever specific evaluative objectives for merit raises or promotions have been met. The general trend, however, is to make sure that the supervisor discusses the appraisal with their employees, allowing employees to discuss areas of agreement and disagreement. The supervisor should emphasize positive work performance—those areas in which the employee has met or exceeded expectations as well as areas that need improvement.
- **Determine future performance goals:** A critical aspect of PA is the use of goal-setting. How specifically or rigidly these goals are to be pursued is determined by the appraisal method used. Even if goals are only broadly discussed, setting goals for the employee's future appraisal period is critical because it gives the employee direction for continued or improved performance. When leaving the appraisal discussion, an employee is more likely to feel comfortable knowing how past performance has been viewed and what needs to be accomplished to meet future expectations.

2.2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.2.1 Goal-Setting Theory

Goal-setting theory had been proposed by Edwin Locke in 1968. This theory suggests that the individual goals established by an employee play an important role in motivating him for superior performance. This is because the employees keep following their goals. If these goals are not achieved, they either improve their performance or modify

the goals to make them more realistic. If the performance improves, it will result in the achievement of the performance management system's aims (Salaman, 2009).

The theory further highlights methods that connect goals to performance results, direct thought to priorities, and arouse effort; methods that challenge individuals to get knowledge and skills to increase their output of achievements; and difficult objectives. The theory stresses the importance of PM in setting and accepting objectives aligned with performance that can be calculated and managed. Goal setting has been recognized as a way of tracking achievement and performance in different situations and under different principles. Managers are required to set clear targets and challenging objectives and explain what is expected to lead to a high level of performance. Managers should be in agreement with the junior in line with the required qualifications (Cascio, 2013).

Locke and Latham provide a well-developed goal-setting theory of motivation. The theory emphasizes the important relationship between goals and performance. Research supports predictions that the most effective performance seems to result when goals are specific and challenging, when they are used to evaluate performance and linked to feedback on results, and when they create commitment and acceptance. Goals have a pervasive influence on employee behavior and performance in organizations and management practices (Locke & Latham, 2008). Nearly every modern organization has some form of goal-setting in operation. Programs such as management by objectives (MBO), high-performance work practices, management information systems, benchmarking, stretch targets, systems thinking, and strategic planning include the development of specific goals.

2.2.2 Control Theory

In control theory, as expounded by Thibaut and Walker in 1975, it is assumed that individuals prefer to be in control of decision-making processes through feedback rather than being passive recipients. For example, in a recent study of computer-based performance monitoring, Douthitt and Aiello (2010) reported that employee participation (providing input related to the expression of work process preferences) had a positive impact on perceptions of procedural justice. However, they showed that the ability to control the computer monitoring (whether it was on or off) did not significantly influence perceptions of justice. Their findings suggest that various forms of control (decision and process) may partially determine the perceived fairness of performance appraisals. This can therefore be related to the effect of feedback in performance appraisals on employees' performance. It shows that if the employees are involved through feedback given to them in terms of their performance, they will feel valued and therefore motivated to perform better. The control theory is linked to the feedback variable in the study.

2.2.3 Social Cognitive Theory

Social cognitive theory is a learning theory based on the idea that people learn by observing others. These learned behaviors can be central to one's personality. While social psychologists agree that the environment in which one grows up contributes to behavior, the individual person (and therefore cognition) is just as important. People learn by observing others, with the environment, behavior, and cognition being the chief factors influencing development in a reciprocal triadic relationship. For example, each behavior witnessed can change a person's way of thinking (cognition).

Similarly, the environment one is raised in may influence later behaviors, just as a father's mindset (also cognition) will determine the environment in which his children are raised. There are five core concepts associated with the social cognitive theory framework. These core concepts are observational learning and modeling, outcome expectations, self-efficacy, goal setting, and self-regulation. It is important to note that learning can occur without a change in behavior. According to J.E. Ormrod's general principles of social learning, while a visible change in behavior is the most common proof of learning, it is not absolutely necessary. Social learning theorists say that because people can learn through observation alone, their learning may not necessarily be shown in their performance.

Strong performance requires positive self-beliefs in efficacy in addition to appropriate skills and abilities. Self-efficacy influences computing performance through positive influences about ability and learning by observation (Compeau & Higgins, 2008). Model affect, anxiety, and usage measured personal outcome expectations and behavior toward the use of technology. Performance outcomes influence affect and use (Compeau & Higgins, 2008). Emphasize the means by which individuals exercise personal agency and extra-personal factors in career development. Learning experiences about career interests are mediated by self-efficacy (Lent, 2007). Individuals' success or failure in past experiences can be indexed in social cognitive theory by the psychological construct of self-efficacy. Thus, this theory supports the study variable of performance feedback, which is essential for employees to learn from past shortcomings.

2.2.4 Expectancy Theory

This theory was proposed by Victor Vroom in 1964, and it stresses and focuses on outcomes. According to Lucas and Diener (2007), expectancy theory is a set of decision theories of motivation and performance. Perception plays a vital role in this theory because it emphasizes the cognitive ability to anticipate likely consequences that result from behavioral action (Krentner & Kinicki, 2011). As explained by Vroom (1964), the expectancy theory has two major assumptions: first, individuals have a perception of the concerns that result from their interactive engagements and casual relations among the outcomes, and second, individuals have effective reactions to certain outcomes that are both positive and negative (Lucas & Diener, 2007).

According to this theory, individuals are motivated to perform based on two expectations. Expectancy is the probability that the effort will always lead to desired performance, and second expectancy is that particular performance will lead to preferred outcomes. While some efforts will not be rewarded, the employee will not be motivated to perform a specific task. Expectancy theory relies upon motivators to clarify the causes of behavior at a workstation; external rewards are viewed as motivators that fuel behavior as opposed to intrinsic motivators when behavior is driven by internal forces. The above theory facilitates understanding employee motivation and job performance.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The data for the study was obtained through primary and secondary sources. The primary source was a field survey; the required information was obtained from the various respondents using a self-developed questionnaire. The data obtained was subjected to scrutiny, coding, and descriptive and inferential statistics. The secondary data consists of articles, publications, and other related information on employee performance appraisal. Furthermore, journals and published and unpublished articles were also considered for the study. The population of this study comprises one hundred and sixty (160) respondents from all categories of staff, which constitute (17.8%) of 900 staff of the entire employee at the Lagos State University of Science and Technology (LASUSTECH), Ikorodu, Lagos State.

The data analysis was based on the questionnaire computed for the research work, as the research questions were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computing software. The generated frequencies of the answered questions from the respondents were presented in simple percentages in a tabular form for easy interpretation.

Afterwards, the earlier stated hypotheses were tested using regression analysis. In statistics, regression analysis is a statistical process for estimating the relationship among variables. It includes many techniques for modeling and analyzing several variables when the focus is on the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables. More specifically, regression analysis helps one understand how the typical value of the dependent variable (or criterion variable) changes when any one of the independent variables is varied while the other independent variables are held constant.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND RESULT DISCUSSION

4.1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	90	56.3
Female	70	43.8
Total	160	100.0
Age		
18-25	4	2.5
26-35	22	13.8
36-45	44	27.5
46-55	48	30.0
Above 55 years	42	26.3
Total	160	100.0
Job level		
Junior Staff	20	12.5
Senior Staff	116	72.5
Contract Staff	14	8.8
Top Management	10	6.3
Total	160	100.0
Marital status		

Single	18	11.3
Married	130	81.3
Divorced	4	2.5
Widow/Widower	8	5.0
Total	160	100.0
Years of service		
Less than 2 years	8	5.0
3–10 years	44	27.5
11–20 years	68	42.5
21–30 years	20	12.5
over 30 years	20	12.5
Total	160	100.0
Highest level of formal education		
OND/NCE	4	2.5
HND/ BSC	58	36.3
PGD/M.Sc.	74	46.3
M/Phil/Ph.D	24	15.0
Total	160	100.0
Monthly income		
Less than 50 000	12	7.5
51 000–100 000	22	13.8
101 000–150 000	16	10.0
151 000–200 000	18	11.3
201 000–250 000	18	11.3
251 000–300 000	14	8.8
Over 300,000	60	37.5
Total	160	100.0

Source: Researchers output, 2023

The researcher reveals the gender of the sampled respondents as follows: 56.3% are male and 43.8% are female. It can be confirmed that the study area is dominated by male respondents. The research also reveals a larger percentage of the respondents are between the ages of 46 and 55 (30%), 2.5% are between 18 and 25, 13.8% are between 26 and 35, 27.5% are between 36 and 45, and 26.3% are above 55 years, respectively. The research reveals the job level of the respondents as follows: 12.5% are junior staff, 72.5% are senior staff, 8.8% are contract staff, and 6.3% are top management. It is evident that the majority of the respondents are senior staff. It also reveals a larger percentage of the respondents, which amounts to 81.3 percent, are married, 11.3% are single, 2.5% are divorced, and 5.0% are widows or widowers, respectively.

The years of service of the sampled respondents are as follows: 5% are less than 2 years old, 27.5% are between 3 and 10 years old, 42.5% are between 11 and 20 years old, 12.5% are between 21 and 30 years old, and respondents over 30 years old are also 12.5%. The highest level of formal education among the respondents is as follows: 2.5% are OND/NCE holders, 36.3% are HND/BSC holders, 46.3% are PGD/M.Sc. holders, and 15% are M.Phil./Ph.D. holders, which therefore shows the larger percentage of the sampled population has PGD/M.Sc. The income level of the sampled respondents is as follows: 7.5% earn less than 50, 000; 13.8% earn between 51, 000 and 100, 000; 10% earn between 101, 000 and 150, 000; 11.3% earn between 151, 000 and 200, 000; 11.3% earn between 201, 000 and 250, 000; 8.8% earn between 251, 000 and 300, 000; and 37.5% earn over 300, 000, respectively.

4.2 FACTORS THAT DETERMINE EMPLOYEES' PRODUCTIVITY

The research aims to identify factors that determine employees' productivity in the sampled location. Hence, the employees of the organization rate the effectiveness of performance appraisals in the institution as follows: 21.3 said it has been highly efficient; 60% said it is efficient; 10% are undecided; 6.3% are not efficient; and 2.5% are highly non-efficient. The research, therefore, established that performance appraisal is efficient in the organization. The research also reveals how often the respondents receive performance appraisals: 85% said annually, 1.3% said every two years, 8.8% said every three years, and 5% said over 5 years. The research therefore confirms that the respondents are appraised annually. The research further reveals the impact of regular performance appraisals on the respondent's motivation to improve performance. 87.5% said yes, while 12.5% said no; hence, it can be established that performance appraisal has played a significant role in the motivation of the sampled respondents towards the improvement of their performance.

Furthermore, the research reveals the significance of leadership in the productivity of workers. 65% strongly agreed, 31.3% agreed, 1.3% were undecided, and 2.5% disagreed, and the research findings established that leadership is fundamental to the productivity of workers. Also, the relationship between the university management and employees is found to be fundamental to the development of the university, as 55.6% of the respondents strongly agreed, 31.9% agreed, 1.3% were undecided, 6.9% disagreed, and 4.4% strongly disagreed, respectively.

The research is aimed at revealing if the opportunity for personal growth, achievement, recognition, and reward has been instrumental to an employee's productivity. 52.5% strongly agreed, 38.8% agreed, 5% were undecided, 1.3% disagreed, and 2.5% strongly disagreed. The research established opportunities for personal growth, achievement, recognition, reward, etc. that have been instrumental to the employee's productivity. The research further reveals that the majority of the respondents disagreed that the comfort derived from the work environment and offices has played a significant role in employees' productivity, as 36.9% strongly agreed, 50% agreed, 4.4% undecided, 4.4% disagreed, and strongly disagreed, respectively.

4.3 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE APPRAISAL PROCESS ON WORKERS PRODUCTIVITY

The research is aimed at revealing if Human Resource Management (HRM) adopts structured performance appraisals in the evaluation of their employees' performance in the organization. 15% strongly agreed, 66.3% agreed, 12.5% were undecided, 5% disagreed, and 1.3% strongly disagreed. The research established that human resource management (HRM) adopts structured performance appraisals in the evaluation of its employees. The research also reveals whether human resource management (HRM) has been efficient in managing the university workforce. The analysis reveals 10% strongly agreed, 46.3% agreed, 26.3% undecided, 16.3% disagreed, and 1.3% strongly disagreed, respectively. The analysis confirms that the HRM unit has been efficient in managing the university workforce.

The research is also aimed at revealing if HRM has played a significant role in the recruitment, training, and development of employees to boost their productivity. 23.8% of the respondents strongly agreed, 41.3% agreed, 20% were undecided, 12.5% disagreed, and 2.5% strongly disagreed. Since the research reveals a larger percentage of agreed respondents, it can therefore be concluded that HRM has played a significant role in the recruitment, training, and development of employees to boost their productivity. The research also reveals if the goals of organizations have been a yardstick for measuring organization performance, which has been helpful for the Human Resource Unit. 15.6% strongly agreed, 58.1% agreed, 15.6% were undecided, 5% disagreed, and 5.6% strongly disagreed, respectively. It can be concluded that organization goals have been a yardstick for measuring organization performance, which has been helpful for the Human Resource Unit.

The research reveals that performance appraisal is an indispensable aspect of the university; hence, it has played a significant role in its productivity. 19.4% strongly agreed. 60.6% agreed, 8.8% were undecided, 6.9% disagreed, and 4.4% strongly disagreed, respectively. It is, however, important to mention that performance appraisal is an indispensable aspect of the university; hence, it has played a significant role in its productivity. Furthermore, the majority of the sampled respondents agreed that positive performance appraisal at the university is subject to job attitudes such as job satisfaction and commitment. The majority of the respondents opined that in order for the university to experience improved development and employee job satisfaction, the management strictly adheres to appraisal outcomes, with 26.3% strongly agreeing, 51.3% agreeing, 10% undecided, 11.3% disagreeing, and 1.3% strongly disagreeing.

The research is also aimed at revealing if, due to management preference, appraisal reports and outcomes are not often adhered to or properly reported. 12.5% strongly agreed, 42.5% agreed, 14.4% were undecided, 27.5% disagreed, and 3.1% strongly disagreed. The analysis reveals the majority of the respondents agreed with most of the appraisal report, and outcomes are not often adhered to or properly reported due to management preference. The research is also aimed at revealing if the university management does not have a structured, formal performance appraisal system and appropriate rewards in place. 6.3% strongly agreed, 22.5% agreed, 12.5% were undecided, 50% disagreed, and 8.8% strongly disagreed, respectively. The research concludes that the university management has a structured, formal appraisal system and appropriate rewards in place.

The research also reveals that performance appraisals are often used by management to further improve and develop employees' abilities and potential. 30% strongly agreed, 40% agreed, 18.8% were undecided, 7.5% disagreed, and 3.8% strongly disagreed. The research thus confirmed that performance appraisals are often used by university management to further improve and develop employees' abilities and potential. Furthermore, the respondents affirmed that a structured performance appraisal system has a substantial impact on other aspects of human resources: 19.4% strongly agreed, 68.8% agreed, 3.1% undecided, 5.6% disagreed, and 3.1% strongly disagreed. The implication of this is that the majority agreed that a structured performance appraisal system has a substantial impact on other aspects of human resources. The research is also aimed at revealing if a well-orchestrated appraisal exercise by HRM has helped reconcile management with the employees. 17.5% strongly agreed, 61.3% agreed, 8.8% were undecided, 11.3% disagreed, and 1.3% strongly

disagreed, respectively. The research affirmed that a well-orchestrated appraisal exercise by HRM has helped reconcile management with the employees.

The research is also aimed at revealing if the global economic depression has put major constraints on university management and led to non-proportional rewards for staff. 11.3% strongly agreed, 50% agreed, 25% were undecided, 11.3% disagreed, and 2.5% disagreed. Hence, the research reveals the majority of the respondents do not agree that management invests a huge sum of money in reward and recognition with a view to boosting workers motivation. The majority of the respondents also disagreed that appraisal exercises often result in negative effects because the decisions made are unfair and inaccurate and the outcomes are biasedly implemented. 8.8% strongly agreed, 26.3% agreed, 17.5% were undecided, 40% disagreed, and 7.5% strongly disagreed. Therefore, the research established a positive correlation between performance appraisal and productivity as it relates to rewards and the productivity of workers.

4.4 TEST OF HYPOTHESIS

S/No	Hypotheses	R	R-Square	Significance
1	H ₀ : No relationship exists between an employee's performance appraisal and their productivity.	0.329	0.108	0.003
2	H ₀ : A well-structured appraisal process does not have a significant impact on employee satisfaction.	0.372	0.139	0.019
3	Staff appraisal and appropriate reward do not have a significant impact on staff motivation.	0.560	0.313	0.00

Source: Researcher output, 2023

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULT

In an attempt to measure the success of the regression in the prediction of dependent variable value within the sample, that is, the significant changes in the dependent variable accounted for by little changes in the independent variables, For the first hypothesis, it was helpful in measuring the level of relationship that exists between employee performance appraisal and employee productivity in the sampled location. It also revealed whether a well-structured appraisal process has a significant impact on employee satisfaction, according to the second hypothesis. Furthermore, it measures staff appraisal and appropriate reward impact on staff motivation for the third hypothesis, respectively.

The R- value measures the nature of the relationship that exists between the sampled variables. The hypotheses reveal R-values of 0.329, 0.372, and 0.560. The research established a positive relationship between the sampled dependent variables and independent variables, respectively. The implication of this is that a fraction of the variance of the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables.

The estimated R-square result indicated the percentage changes in the dependent variable that are accounted for by the independent variables. The first hypothesis is 0.108; the implication of the result is that an employee's performance appraisal accounts for 10% of changes in the productivity of workers, while 90% are accounted for by other variables outside the model. The second hypothesis is 0.139, which reveals that holding other variables constant, a well-structured performance appraisal process will result in a 13% impact on employee satisfaction, while 87% is accounted for by other variables outside the model. The third hypothesis reveals an R-square value of 0.313. Holding all variables constant, appropriate rewards for members of staff during appraisal exercises will result in a 31% impact on staff motivation, while 69% of the changes are not accounted for in the model or connected to other variables outside the model.

In an attempt to draw a logical conclusion from the earlier stated hypotheses, they were tested at a 95% confidence interval. The initially stated null hypothesis will be rejected if the p-value is less than <0.05. The data analysis thus reveals a significance value (p-value) of 0.003. Hence, the first hypothesis reveals a significant value less than 0.05; it is therefore pertinent to adopt the alternative hypothesis by saying a relationship exists between an employee's performance appraisal and their productivity. The rejection of the null hypothesis is due to the lack of statistical support.

The significance (p-value) for the second hypothesis is 0.019. Considering the significance of the validation of the earlier stated hypothesis, it is therefore pertinent to reject the earlier stated null hypothesis, which states that a well-structured appraisal process does not have a significant impact on employee satisfaction. It is therefore pertinent to adopt the alternative hypothesis by saying that a well-structured appraisal process has a significant impact on employee satisfaction. The rejection of the null hypothesis is due to the lack of statistical support.

The significance value (p-value) for the third hypothesis is 0.00. Considering the significance of the validation of the earlier stated hypothesis, it is therefore pertinent to reject the earlier stated null hypothesis, which states that staff appraisal and appropriate reward do not have a significant impact on staff motivation. It is therefore pertinent to adopt the

alternative hypothesis by saying that staff appraisal and appropriate reward have a significant impact on staff motivation. The rejection of the null hypothesis is due to the lack of statistical support.

5.1 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The research established that performance appraisal has played a significant role in the efficient management of the university; hence, it has played a significant role in the motivation of the staff towards the improvement of their performance. Furthermore, the research reveals the significance of leadership in the productivity of the workers, which reveals leadership is considered fundamental to the productivity of workers. Also, the relationship between the university management and employees is found to be fundamental to the development of the university. The research further reveals the staff is appraised annually, and the university has been helpful in the personal growth and achievement of its staff through recognition and reward, which has been instrumental to employee productivity. However, the research reveals that the majority of the respondents claimed the work environment had not played a significant role in their productivity.

The research reveals the HRM unit adopts structured performance appraisals in the evaluation of their employees' performance at the university, which has played a significant role in employee motivation over the years. Furthermore, human resource management (HRM) has been efficient in managing the university workforce. Also, the HRM played a significant role in the recruitment, training, and development of employees to boost their productivity; the goals of organizations have been a yardstick for measuring organization performance, which has been helpful for the Human Resource Unit.

It is important to mention that performance appraisal is an indispensable aspect of the university; hence, it has played a significant role in its productivity. Furthermore, the majority of positive performance appraisals at the university are subject to job attitudes such as job satisfaction and commitment. The majority of the respondents opined that in order for the university to experience improved development and employee job satisfaction, the management must strictly adhere to appraisal outcomes. Hence, the university management has a structured, formal appraisal system and appropriate rewards in place, which further improve and develop employees' abilities and potential.

The research affirmed that a well-orchestrated appraisal exercise by HRM has helped reconcile management with the employees; however, the global economic depression does not put constraints on university management in the implementation of appropriate rewards. However, the majority of the respondents do not agree that management invests a huge sum of money in reward and recognition with a view to boosting workers motivation. The majority of the respondents disagreed appraisal exercises often result in negative effects because the decisions made are unfair and inaccurate and the outcomes are biasedly implemented. Finally, the research established a positive correlation between performance appraisal and productivity as it relates to rewards and the productivity of workers.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The role of leaders in the university is considered fundamental to the productivity of workers in the university; hence, the university management should maintain a good relationship with them with a view to avoiding industrial action that may hamper academic activities in the institution.
2. The significance of personal growth and development cannot be overemphasized in an academic environment; hence, the university management should avail the members of staff more avenues for personal growth, achievement, recognition, and reward, which will further enhance the employees productivity;
3. The university management should further improve the work environment and staff offices, which may aid in the eradication of psychological problems, pains, stress, and ill-health and will also play a pivotal role in enhancing staff productivity.
4. The HR management should further improve the structured performance appraisal system in the evaluation of its employees to enhance its efficiency and create further confidence in the members of staff.
5. The HRM unit should further improve the training and development of employees, taking into consideration the organization's goals, which will be helpful in boosting productivity among workers.
6. The university management should put in place a well-orchestrated appraisal exercise, which will further help reconcile the management with the employees;
7. The university management should put in place effective performance appraisal with appropriate reward, which will further help in effective service delivery;
8. If the appraisal exercise result is not fair and accurate, and in addition, if the outcome is biasedly implemented, this will affect the morale of staff; hence, the university management should ensure all exercise results are accurate and strictly implemented.

5.3 CONCLUSION

The significance of a well-structured appraisal system cannot be overemphasized in an organization; however, the implementation of the appraisal outcome is as good as the appraisal result itself; hence, university management should ensure appropriate rewards are put in place in conformity with the appraisal result; however, in a situation whereby the management is not financially capable, there must be a compromise between the staff and the management. It is important to reiterate that a shabby appraisal system and inappropriate rewards corrupt the system, which may result in internal crises. Therefore, the result of the appraisal exercise should be adjudged fair by a member of staff.

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